

The Legal Landscape of Over-the-Top Platforms in India: Implications for India's Cyberspace Regulation

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Introduction

The digital revolution has opened up new ways of communication and entertainment for billions of people. We use internet-based platforms that provide more conveniences than just conventional voice calls and text messaging, whether we are conversing with our peers on WhatsApp, attending a meeting on Google Meet, watching a show on Netflix, or following a star on Instagram. These platforms are called Over-the-Top (OTT) platforms, because they deliver their services over the internet, bypassing the traditional telecom operations. OTT platforms include a wide range of applications that enable personal, group, and mass communication and broadcasting, such as messaging, video conferencing, social media, streaming, and even online gaming. But while OTT platforms have empowered us to access diverse and engaging content at our fingertips, they have also raised some challenges and concerns for the government and the society. In India, the government has proposed a draft Telecommunication bill that would regulate OTT platforms under a common framework, regardless of their different features and functions.

The bill has been criticized by policy researchers and civil society groups who specialize in privacy protection and promoting minimal regulatory requirements for tech-based startups.¹ The bill is too broad and vague especially, in context of defining OTT platforms that are also treated as telecom companies.

The growth of internet users in India is driven by various factors, such as the availability and affordability of smartphones and mobile data, the expansion of broadband infrastructure, the emergence of digital platforms and services, and the rising digital literacy and awareness among the people. The growth of internet usage has enabled the functioning of OTT platforms. India is one of the largest and fastest-growing online markets in the world. According to a report by Cisco, India will have more than 907 million internet users by 2023, accounting for nearly 64% of the population. This is a significant increase from 2018 when there were only

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398 million internet users, or 29% of the population.² India's internet user base is diverse and heterogeneous, with different languages, preferences, and needs. The internet has become an integral part of many aspects of life in India, such as education, health, entertainment, commerce, governance, and social interaction.

The paper analyzes the prevailing legal landscape that governs the Over-the-Top platforms. The issue of what is known as "blanket interpretation" is at the centre of the criticism of draft Telecom Bill, 2022 that was open for public consultation till December 2022. The paper further analyzes the nature and types of OTT platforms based on their functionality, followed by a suggestion of how this OTT platform regulation can benefit if the government considers how to regulate the data exchange in the ecology of cyberspace, and how interpretation of OTT platforms based on their functionality can help in enabling innovations in technology that relies on open, free, and a rules-based internet.

Draft Telecommunication Bill 2022: A Critical Analysis

Draft Telecommunication Bill 2022 was recently put up for public consultation, and is meant to repeal the outdated Indian Telegraph Act, 1885, Wireless Telegraph Act, 1933, and Telegraph Wires Act 1950 to replace them with a new legal framework for telecom industry.³ The bill aims to exhaustively include latest broadcasting-based communication technologies within the ambit of government regulation. Quoting Section 2(21) from draft Telecommunication Bill 2022, the broadcasting based communication includes "electronic mail (email), voice mail, voice, video and data communication services, audiotex services, videotex services, fixed and mobile services, internet and broadband services, satellite based communication services, internet based communication services, in-flight and maritime connectivity services, interpersonal communications services, machine to machine communication services, over-the-top (OTT) communication services which is made available to users by telecommunication"

As per the draft telecom bill, OTT platforms such as email, WhatsApp, Facebook, Netflix, Twitter, Amazon Shopping, Zomato Food Delivery, Uber et.al. are subjected to similar licensing and regulatory requirements that are applicable to telecom companies, regardless of the difference between the business of "Internet Service Providers" (ISP) i.e., the telecom and broadband companies who develop the infrastructure required to create the internet, and

“Internet-Based Services Provider” (IBSP) i.e., the platforms who rely on the services of ISP to sell their products or services on the internet.

This can be understood by a simple example. A user pays Reliance Jio or Bharti Airtel, (the ISPs) for internet services, and Netflix, (the IBSP) for the content that it provides. Netflix allows the users to stream movies, series documentaries, and other motion picture-based entertainment material from the data stored in their servers through internet. The distribution of the services of Netflix relies on the quality of the internet that telecom companies (ISP) provide to its customers. Better the fidelity of network and quality of connection, better quality of movies can be streamed online through internet. The same user also uses WhatsApp another IBSP, for inter-personal communication (personal chats), group communication and broadcasting (chatting groups and message broadcasting), that also relies on the same ISP that also enables Netflix in the above example.

Treating these two OTT platforms i.e., Netflix and WhatsApp to the same standards under the blanket term of ‘telecommunication companies’ is fallacious since the purpose and legality involved behind their functioning are completely different. Internet is the common means through which such OTT services are consumed by the society at large. The resources required behind establishing a telecom company (ISP) are completely different from an OTT (IBSP) company and so will be the regulations. The former involves investments in acquiring spectrums, building physical infrastructure for telecom towers, or fiber optical cables, and maintenance of call centers, auxiliary branches & back-offices, while operations of OTT platforms involve acquisition of server farms, creating network systems, generate and/or moderate content on the platform, develop user interface, process the user data, and assure integrity of the network.

Significance of OTT platforms

OTT platforms are the backbone of the modern-day internet and are responsible for its widespread use. They play a significant role in communication, content sharing, and networking. A recent study conducted by T. Koch et.al. found that 89% of respondents reported getting contacted by recruiters if they had an updated LinkedIn profile.⁴ (a professional social media application- part of ‘internet-based communication’ service as mentioned in the Sec

2(21) of Draft Telecom Bill, 2022). This suggests that having a presence on LinkedIn can increase an individual's chances of getting hired.

According to another study conducted by A. Mason et al., social media can be a powerful tool for businesses to activate consumer needs and promote their products or services. By engaging in brand conversations, virtual messaging, and other social media platforms, businesses can increase brand awareness and encourage consumer-to-consumer interactions to share product experiences. Many businesses also utilize influencers such as celebrities and athletes to build product awareness, given their millions of followers and potential influence on consumer decision-making. Furthermore, marketing and advertising agencies often have specific departments focused on creating search engine optimized content to improve their products or services' search engine ranking. These services have become an integral part of our daily activities, as we rely on them to connect with others, search for information, and make purchasing decisions.

Types of OTT Platforms

OTT (Over-The-Top) platforms provide various types of services, and we can categorize them based on their primary purpose. The first type is communication-based, and it includes messaging applications like WhatsApp, Telegram, Signal et.al. These platforms are designed for users to communicate and share various types of data, including text, images, videos, audios, and documents with each other. The second type is content-based, which includes streaming platforms like Netflix, Prime Video, and Spotify. These platforms provide users with access to a vast collection of videos and audios, which they can watch or listen to at any time. The primary objective of these platforms is to broadcast high-quality content to their users. The third type of service is a combination of communication and content broadcasting. Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, Twitch, YouTube, multiplayer online games, et.al, are examples of such services. These platforms enable users to create and share user-generated content with others, which can include anything from photos, audios, and videos to articles and blogs. The platforms are responsible for creating a shared experience for users on a digital plane that enables collaboration for generating and sharing information. Users can increase their reach and expand their network of connections by generating and sharing their content on these platforms.

Fig 1: Types of Over-the-Top Platforms

The Case of Online Gaming

One of the most popular and profitable sectors of the internet is the online gaming industry, which offers a variety of games and platforms for users to enjoy. Online gaming allows people to connect and collaborate with others from different backgrounds and locations, creating a sense of community and belonging. However, this also raises some challenges and concerns regarding the regulation and moderation of online gaming activities. Some online games may contain content or themes that are offensive or inappropriate for some users, such as violence, nudity, or religious symbols. Moreover, some users may engage in abusive or hateful behavior towards others based on their ethnicity, gender, or beliefs. This can create a hostile and toxic environment for online gaming communities, affecting their enjoyment and well-being.⁵

Another issue is how to prevent online gaming platforms from being used for criminal or terrorist purposes. Some online games have features that allow users to communicate privately with each other through voice or text messages. These features can be exploited by malicious actors who use them to coordinate attacks, spread propaganda, or recruit followers. For example, some terrorist groups have used online games to communicate with their members and sympathizers, avoiding detection by law enforcement agencies.⁶

The increasing sophistication at each level of value chain on these OTT platforms suggests that a blanket law for governing these platforms will not be efficient for the long-term regulation of telecom and internet industry as they are becoming more collaborative and engaging. While

we discussed about the change in which the content is being consumed, there is also a change in how content over the internet is being created.

How is content generated and shared on OTT platforms?

1. On Content and Communication Platforms

The broadcasting platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube etc. who fall under the ambit of both content-based and communication services, need a separate legal definition, independent of the blanket term i.e., telecom company. The unique aspect of these platforms is; there is no water tight distinction between the user and producer of the content broadcasted on platforms. The platform providers use the content created by the user and broadcast it on the network by gauging the engagement rate of the posts fed into the algorithms that decides what post should reach to maximum number of audiences who share similar experiences and interests.⁷ These algorithms are kept under utter secrecy by the social media companies.

The algorithm, however, does not rely on user engagement itself. There are cases where highly engaged posts may not be promoted by the platform, also known as 'shadow ban' as they go against the moderation policy of the platform. The content moderation and legal matters handled within these platforms is highly guarded.⁸ Individuals having expertise in law, politics, governance etc. form the board of content moderation in these companies.⁹ There are lobbies and pressure groups who intend to leverage their political power to influence the content moderation policies of these platforms, creating a thin line between content moderation and State censorship. Given the transnational nature of these service providers, it should be imperative that national security concerns of the State where these platforms are being used, are considered while deciding the content moderation policies. The current Information Technology Act, 2011 of India provides social media companies legal immunity in case their platform becomes a source of fake or misleading information. While they are obliged to have a strict moderation policy, the recent case of Twitter Files shows how political parties influence the moderation policies of social media companies and keeps a strong check on what type of information it allows to flow in society at large.¹⁰

2. On Convenience Platforms: Impact on Ease of Business

When the government imposes the same legal rules on internet-based services as they do on telecom companies, they overlook the unique aspects of the internet industry and its impact on society. These services are interconnected, forming the ecosystem of internet-based services. One of the most significant features of the internet is its ability to create convenient consumer services that make life easier. This openness allows for innovations that reduce the barriers to entry that existed in traditional business models. Examples of these services include food aggregators like Swiggy and Zomato, e-commerce websites like Amazon and Flipkart, and ride-sharing applications like Uber and Ola. However, if the draft telecom bill is applied, all these businesses could be interpreted as telecom companies, regardless of their actual function. Regulating these non-telecom ecosystems with the same standards as traditional telecom companies will stifle innovation in the computer science domain. This innovation is critical to the growth of the tech startup ecosystem, which is worth ₹3 trillion in India, according to the Cabinet member and Union Commerce & Industry Minister, Mr. Piyush Goyal.¹¹ A new legal framework based on the functionality of each OTT platform is required for long-term regulatory stability in cyberspace.

Regulate user data to regulate OTT platforms

Data forms the basis of the ecology of OTT platforms. All activities in cyberspace can be traced through exchange of data between service provider and user. Data is the currency of the modern-day internet. In order to regulate the internet industry, the focus should be on regulating the transaction of data. For this, a separate regulation called personal data protection bill is underway that emphasizes on defining the parties to the transactions of data within the cyberspace.

The draft Personal Data Protection Bill that was also put for public consultation distinguishes between the parties to transaction within the ecology of cyberspace based on exchange of data between each of the parties. As per the bill, the user of the services is interpreted as the data principal. The platform that collects and stores data is interpreted as data fiduciary and the platform that processes the stored/collected data is interpreted as the data processor. Regulating

the activities of all these actors within the cyberspace will be more helpful to ensure user privacy and security.

Distinguishing between the OTT platforms based on their functionality enables the lawmakers to take cognizance of user privacy and State regulation for ensuring safe cyberspace. While the content of the data must follow the triad of encryption (confidentiality, integrity, and availability), keeping track on the data exchange can serve the purpose of ensuring security. OTT platforms can also be held accountable in case the service provider fails to comply with the data regulations.

Conclusion

The paper provides a critical analysis of the draft Indian Telecommunication Bill, 2022 and its implications for the regulation of over-the-top (OTT) platforms in India. The paper argues that the draft Bill adopts a broad and outdated definition of telecommunication services that includes internet-based and OTT communication services such as WhatsApp, Skype, Netflix, etc. The paper contends that this approach is problematic for several reasons.

- It ignores the diversity and innovation of OTT platforms that offer different types of services such as messaging, voice, video, content, e-commerce, etc. and have different impacts on the telecom sector and the society at large. It creates an uneven playing field between OTT platforms and telecom service providers (TSPs) by subjecting them to the same licensing and regulatory regime, without considering their different cost structures, revenue models, and market dynamics.
- It imposes excessive and unnecessary regulatory burdens on OTT platforms that may hamper their growth and development, especially for start-ups and small players who may not have the resources or expertise to comply with complex and varied rules and obligations.
- It infringes on the rights and interests of OTT users by exposing them to potential surveillance, censorship, data breaches, and service disruptions due to government interference or TSP discrimination.

The paper suggests that instead of treating OTT platforms as telecom services, the government should adopt a more nuanced and flexible approach that recognizes their distinct features and functions. The paper proposes that the government should:

- Adopt a clear and consistent definition of OTT platforms based on their functionality rather than their delivery mode i.e., the internet.
- Classify OTT platforms into different categories based on their nature, scope, impact, and public interest value such as communication OTTs, content OTTs, transactional OTTs, etc. and apply different levels of regulation accordingly.
- Adopt a light-touch and principles-based regulation for OTT platforms that focuses on ensuring consumer protection, data privacy, network security, fair competition, and innovation.
- Encourage self-regulation and co-regulation by OTT platforms through industry codes of conduct, best practices, standards, etc. that are aligned with the government's objectives and values.
- Promote cooperation and coordination between OTT platforms and TSPs to address issues such as interconnection, quality of service, network management, revenue sharing, etc. through mutual agreements or industry forums.
- Engage in regular consultation and dialogue with all stakeholders including OTT platforms, TSPs, consumers, civil society groups, academia, etc. to understand their perspectives and concerns and to foster trust and transparency.

The paper concludes that by adopting a more balanced and forward-looking approach to regulating OTT platforms, the government can harness their potential for economic growth, social development, digital inclusion, and good governance while safeguarding the rights and interests of all stakeholders.

Notes

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